

Studies on the Formation of some Molybdomalates

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The formation of molybdomalates has been studied by conductance, viscosity, and cryoscopic measurements. Several molybdomalates have been prepared and their structures discussed.

Henderson *et al.*¹ prepared alkali molybdomalates by boiling MoO_3 with the solution of primary malates without undergoing reduction. Mazzucchelli *et al.*²⁻⁴ studied the formation of complexes between malic acid and molybdic acid and observed the formation of the complexes $\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{MoO}_3$ and $\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{MoO}_3$ by optical rotation, cryoscopic, and electrolytic measurements. They also concluded the formation of the complexes $\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{MoO}_4$ and $2\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{MoO}_4$ between permolybdic acid and malic acid by cryoscopic and conductance measurements. Darmois⁵⁻⁷ studied the influence of ammonium molybdate on the rotatory power of malic acid and succeeded in isolating the ammonium compound. He isolated the sodium salt also and prepared⁶ many salts of the complex acid $2\text{MoO}_3 \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_5$, calculated the molecular weights of the Na and NH_4 compounds and studied⁷ the formation of $4\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 2\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_5$ and $\text{MoO}_3 \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_5$ by rotation and *pH* measurements. Honnelaitre⁸ observed that the titration curves of molybdic and malic acids by NH_4OH and NaOH as well as of the mixtures of these acids showed the formation of the complexes $n \cdot \text{MoO}_3 \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_5$ ($n=1$ to 2). By optical measurements Andrew⁹ concluded the formation of a monobasic acid with a closed six-membered ring from mixtures of malic acid and molybdates in presence and absence of citrates. Delsal¹⁰ applied polarometric and electrometric methods for the study of complexes between malic acid and several hexivalent and trivalent metals. Richardson¹¹ prepared some complexes of α -hydroxy-acids with molybdic and tungstic acids by ion-exchange method. According to Baillie and Brown¹², 1:1 complex ion of molybdate ion with malic acid is a weaker dibasic acid than the parent organic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of B. D. H. or Merck's "extra pure" quality. Conductivity water was used throughout the titration procedure.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, **75**, 542.
2. *Gazzetta*, 1913, **43**, 26.
3. *Ibid.*, 1914, **44**, 116.
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5. *Compt. rend.*, 1920, **171**, 348; 1921, **172**, 1486; 1922, **174**, 204.
6. Darmois *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1926, **182**, 269; 1923, **177**, 762.
7. Darmois, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1926, **39**, 1515, 723.
8. *Ann. Chim.* 1925, **3**, 5.
9. *Proc. Iowa Acad. Sci.*, 1925, **32**, 267.
10. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, **35**, 350.
11. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1960, **13**, 84
12. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3691.

Sodium molybdate ($0.04M$) and malic acid ($0.0442M$) stock solutions were prepared. Sodium molybdate solution was standardised by estimating molybdenum as lead molybdate and malic acid solution, by titrating it against a standard sodium hydroxide solution.

Conductometric Titrations

Sodium molybdate stock solution (5 ml), diluted to 65 ml, was placed on a magnetic stirrer and the dip cell was properly dipped in solution. The titration cell was immersed in a thermostat to control the temperature within $\pm 0.5^\circ$. The conductance was measured by a Mullard conductivity bridge, type E 7566, with direct-reading visual balance detector. Malic acid (0.1 ml) was run down every time from a microburette. The solution was stirred well and the conductance recorded. In the reverse titrations, 5 ml of malic acid stock solution was taken in the cell and titrated against the stock sodium molybdate solution.

FIG. 1

Conductance was plotted against the volume of malic acid. (Fig. 1, curve I) and sodium molybdate (Fig. 1, curve II). The equivalence points were taken as the points of intersection of the two portions of the curves. Direct as well as reverse titrations indicated the formation of two types of complexes, one in molar ratio of 1:1 and other in 1:2 of sodium molybdate and malic acid.

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TABLE I

No.	Compounds.	Colour.	% Mo.		% Other metal.		% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		% H ₂ O.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Calc.
1.	Ag ₂ [(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·H ₂ O	Dirty white	18.16.	18.81	42.67	42.36	9.39	9.41	1.20	1.18	..	..
2.	Pb[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)] ₂ .H ₂ O	White	18.56	19.14	42.23	41.34	..	..	..	..	4.12	3.59
3.	Hg[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·H ₂ O	Light yellow	18.85	19.40	40.01	40.56	..	..	..	..	3.98	3.64
4.	PbO[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·3H ₂ O	White	16.98	16.60	39.26	40.15	..	..	..	..	9.67	9.34
5.	ZrO[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·4H ₂ O	White	20.34	21.08	19.82	20.04	10.42	10.54	2.70	2.64	..	..
6.	ZrO[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·2H ₂ O	White	22.42	22.80	21.44	21.76	11.32	11.45	1.95	1.91	..	..
7.	Ca[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·3H ₂ O	White	25.51	25.93	10.99	10.81	..	..	..	..	15.02	14.60
8.	Sr[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·2H ₂ O	White	23.32	24.01	21.35	21.93	..	..	..	..	9.46	9.01
9.	Ba[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·3H ₂ O	White	20.22	20.52	28.04	29.40	10.15	10.27	2.20	2.14	..	..
10.	Ni[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·3H ₂ O	Green	25.52	24.08	15.25	15.10	..	..	..	..	14.42	13.90
11.	Co[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·3H ₂ O	Pink	25.46	24.67	15.37	15.10	12.29	12.34	2.63	2.57	..	..
12.	Zn[(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·4H ₂ O	Faint blue	22.73	23.20	14.02	15.62	..	..	..	..	18.29	17.42
13.	Fe ₂ [(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)] ₃ ·3H ₂ O	Dirty yellow	27.08	28.95	11.45	11.23	..	..	..	..	5.93	5.43
14.	UO ₂ [(MoO ₃ .C ₄ H ₄ O ₃)]·2H ₂ O	Light yellow	16.00	16.48	41.58	40.80	8.21	8.25	1.43	1.38	..	..

Solutions of sodium molybdate and malic acid of equimolar strength (0.2149*M*) were prepared in which the volume of sodium molybdate (6 ml) was fixed and that of malic acid varied, the total being made to 50 ml in each case, so that the ratio of sodium molybdate to malic acid was 3:1, 3:2, 3:3, 3:4, 3:5, 3:6, 3:7, and 3:8.

Viscosity Measurements.—The viscosity of these solutions was determined at $30^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$ by Ostwald's method and plotted against the volume of the malic acid. The maxima in the curve (Fig. 2) indicated the formation of the complexes in the ratios of 1:1 and 1:2 of sodium molybdate and malic acid.

FIG. 2

Cryoscopic Measurements.—The freezing points of water and the above solutions were determined by cryoscopic method and the depressions in the freezing point plotted against the concentration of malic acid. The curve (Fig. 3) shows the formation of the complexes in the ratios of 1:1 and 1:2 of sodium molybdate and malic acid.

Isolation of the Compounds

(a). *Pb, Ag, Hg, Th, and Zr Compounds.*—Concentrated solutions of sodium molybdate and malic acid were mixed in molar ratio of 1:1 and left for 24 hr. to attain equilibrium at the room temperature as on boiling, the solution was partly reduced. On addition of rectified spirit to this solution, a liquid compound separated. It was isolated by a

separating funnel and washed with rectified spirit. Aqueous solution of this compound on treatment separately with $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, AgNO_3 , $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$, $\text{Zr}(\text{NO}_3)_4$, and ZrOCl_2 provided the corresponding molybdomalates in which the ratio of the molybdenum malate ion was found to be 1:1. Compounds of Ca, Sr, Ba, Ni, Co, Zn, Fe, and UO_2 could not be prepared by this method owing to solubility of these compounds in water.

FIG. 3

(b). *Ca, Sr, Ba, Ni, and Co Compounds.*—To the equal volumes of the solutions of sodium molybdomalate and CaCl_2 , SrCl_2 , BaCl_2 , $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$, and $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ equal volume of rectified spirit was added. On mixing both the solutions, the corresponding molybdomalates, having the general formula $\text{M}[(\text{MoO}_3 \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_5)] \cdot n \text{H}_2\text{O}$ separated. Care was taken to keep both the solutions clear after addition of rectified spirit.

(c). *Zn, Fe, and UO_2 Compounds.*—To the solution of sodium molybdomalate excess of ZnCl_2 , FeCl_3 , and $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ were added separately and the corresponding molybdomalates separated by adding rectified spirit as ZnCl_2 , FeCl_3 , and $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ were soluble in that solvent.

Analysis.—Molybdenum was estimated as molybdenum oxide after precipitating it as sulphide and subsequent ignition at 525° . Lead, barium, and strontium were estimated as sulphate; silver as chloride; mercury as sulphide; zinc as pyrophosphate; thorium, zirconium, iron, and uranium as oxides; nickel by dimethylglyoxime; cobalt by pyridine method and calcium by converting it into oxalate and titrating it against standard potassium permanganate solution. Water of crystallisation was found by the loss in weight of the compound at 105° . Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by micromethods in a few cases.

DISCUSSION

It is evident from Fig. 1 (curves I-II), Fig. 2, and Fig. 3 that sodium molybdate forms

two types of complexes with malic acid in the molar ratios of 1:1 and 1:2 and their structures may be represented as :

and

Though the physico-chemical measurements show the formation of the latter compound, but it could not be isolated probably due to its being unstable under the experimental conditions.

It is interesting to note that the compounds formed with $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ and $\text{Zr}(\text{NO}_3)_4$ are not the normal molybdomalates but oxymolybdomalates of thorium and zirconium. The probable reactions may be represented as:

[where M = Th or Zr]

It is supported by the fact that the compounds formed by the action of ZrOCl_2 on sodium molybdomalate has a similar composition to that obtained with $\text{Zr}(\text{NO}_3)_4$, except that the former has less water of crystallisation than the latter. The compounds formed by the action of sodium molybdomalate with metallic salts also confirm the existence of complex anionic entity, viz., $[\text{MoO}_3 \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_5]^{2-}$ in solution.

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